

INTERFACE ELEMENT APPROACH TO MODELLING MODE I AND II FRACTURE

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ABSTRACT

An analysis approach based on modelling the interfacial region between plies where delamination occurs is discussed. It is applied to fracture of specimens with small cracks subject to either shear or tension. Results for delamination of tapered specimens with dropped plies loaded in tension are also presented. Comparisons are made with conventional linear elastic fracture mechanics, and it is shown that the interface modelling approach gives better results because it is able to deal with initiation, situations where stresses are high in relation to the yield stress and the effect of friction on mode II delamination.

INTRODUCTION

Fracture mechanics is based on the propagation of a pre-existing crack. In composites there are many cases where fracture occurs without a significant initial crack, for example at free edges or at ply drops. Stress based failure criteria are difficult to apply because of singularities at such features and so it is desirable to make use of a fracture mechanics approach. However, classical methods do not deal with the initiation problem, and cannot be used unless an initial crack is assumed to be present. Even when an initial crack is present, linear elastic fracture mechanics does not give satisfactory results when the interlaminar stresses are high in relation to the yield stress of the matrix. This can easily happen due to the high stresses that can be carried by the fibres compared with the matrix yield stress.

An alternative approach is to model the interfacial region between plies where delamination occurs assuming nonlinear stress-relative deformation characteristics. This can either be done using simple nonlinear springs [1,2] or by means of specially developed interface finite elements [3-7]. Use is made of both stress parameters such as a yield stress, and fracture energy which is the area under the stress-relative deformation curve, thus effectively combining the two different approaches to failure prediction. Interface elements allow fracture to be predicted without initial cracks. This is because the inclusion of stress parameters allows initiation and damage development to be modelled, and means that energy dissipation can occur before final fracture [8]. Interface

elements also give better results than linear elastic fracture mechanics for small crack sizes where the effects of yielding are important.

This paper discusses the interface modelling approach and presents results using it to simulate mode I and II fractures in unidirectional composites.

INTERFACE MODELLING

It is assumed that the composite plies are linear elastic, and that yielding is localised to the resin rich layers between plies. Rather than modelling these as a separate phase, they are taken as being infinitely thin, with duplicate nodes on each side of the interface. This is a reasonable approximation since the resin layers are thin, and it greatly simplifies the problem. The interface characteristics are defined in terms of stress-relative displacement relations for both shear and normal components.

The initial stiffness of the interface is taken as being high to prevent any significant elastic deformation. When a certain stress is reached, yielding is assumed to occur, with further relative deformations taking place at constant stress until a critical displacement corresponding to failure is reached. For the mode I case, the area under the normal stress-relative displacement graph corresponds to the mode I fracture energy, whilst for the mode II case, the area under the shear stress-relative displacement graph corresponds to the mode II fracture energy. This is shown schematically in Fig. 1.

The ABAQUS finite element program was used [10]. All the cases presented here are 2-D, although the approaches can readily be extended to 3-D. Implementation of the interface modelling was done in two different ways. The simplest way is to use two springs between each pair of nodes, one for shear and one for the normal direction. Nonlinear springs are used to define the yielding when a critical stress is reached, and failure at a critical displacement. This approach was used for modelling the effect of small cracks on interlaminar shear strength, and further details can be found elsewhere [2,9].

Where interactions between shear and normal stresses are important, for example in mixed mode delamination or where friction is significant, independent springs can no longer be used. To deal with this an interface element has been developed using the user subroutine capability in ABAQUS [3,11]. It has six nodes, three on each side of the interface, compatible with 8 noded continuum elements. It is still based on springs, with

Figure 1. Interface modelling approach

interfacial stresses calculated from the relative displacements. However, the element can include the effects of interaction between normal and shear response when determining when yield or failure occur and in calculating the forces arising at the interface.

SHORT BEAM SHEAR TESTS WITH SMALL CRACKS

Linear elastic fracture mechanics is unable to explain the effect of small cracks on interlaminar shear strength. Calculations of strain energy release rate indicate that there is not sufficient energy for cracks to propagate unless they are long compared with the span [8]. This precludes fracture propagating from the small cracks which can be expected to be present in the material. It also means that the scatter commonly observed in tests cannot be explained in terms of varying sized defects.

These problems can be overcome using the interface modelling approach [9]. Consider a short beam shear specimen of 24 plies of unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy shown schematically in Fig. 2. The thickness is 3.2 mm, with a length of 25 mm, width of 10 mm and span of 16 mm. This was modelled with four noded 2-D plane stress elements, with a uniform mesh of 50 elements along the length and 24 elements through the thickness i.e. one per ply. The interfaces between each of the plies were represented with springs, allowing yielding to take place throughout the thickness. Nonlinear springs were defined in the shear direction, with an effective shear yield stress of 70 MPa, and a critical displacement giving a fracture energy of 0.66 N/mm. Since it is a pure mode II problem, relative motion in the normal direction was prevented.

Cracks at the mid-plane across the full width of the specimen positioned half way between the loading roller and one of the support rollers were modelled by removing one or more interface springs. The analysis was run with cracks of length from 0.5 to 4 mm. Initial deformation was elastic, followed by yielding and then unstable failure propagating from one end of the crack. The analysis was also run with no crack. Fig. 3 shows the values of the apparent interlaminar shear strength calculated from the load at failure based on the usual equation. Also shown are values calculated using linear elastic fracture mechanics. This was done by evaluating the strain energy release rate for propagation of the initial crack using linear finite element analysis, and equating it to the fracture energy of 0.66 N/mm.

Experimental results were obtained from specimens with small crack like defects produced by including PTFE in the layup [12]. As can be seen, the effect of small cracks is predicted very

Figure 2. Short beam shear specimen with initial crack

Figure 3. Effect of small cracks on interlaminar shear strength

well by the interface modelling approach. The model also works when there is no initial crack, and the results provide a smooth transition between the cases with and without cracks. In contrast the linear elastic fracture mechanics calculation gives strengths which are much too high, and go off to infinity for the case with no initial crack. At large crack lengths the interface modelling and fracture mechanics results become similar as the effect of nonlinearity decreases.

MODE I FRACTURE IN TRANSVERSE TENSION

A domain of unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy with a small central crack subject to tension loading was modelled [13]. This could represent an interlaminar crack in a thick unidirectional plate, or a transverse crack in a 90° ply. In the latter case the interface elements could be considered to be modelling deformations in resin regions between fibres or tows. A quarter model was used, with symmetric boundary conditions, and interface elements along the boundary where crack propagation was expected, as shown in Fig. 4. Six noded

Figure 4. Mode I fracture in transverse tension

Figure 5. Effect of small cracks on transverse tensile strength

interface elements were used, compatible with the 8 noded plane stress continuum elements used to model the composite. A tensile yield stress of 130 MPa was assumed, and a mode I fracture energy of 0.15 N/mm. Due to symmetry this is a pure mode I problem, and no shear deformations arise.

Under an increasing tension loading a small amount of yielding occurred, and then unstable crack propagation. Fig. 5 shows the far field applied stress at failure as a function of crack length. The results from classical linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) are also shown for comparison. It can be seen that for long cracks the results converge. This is because the effect of a small yield zone becomes negligible as the crack length increases. For small crack lengths the interface modelling results approach the tensile yield stress of the material, whereas the linear elastic fracture mechanics results go on increasing. As for the short beam shear specimens, linear elastic fracture mechanics gives unrealistically high strengths. The interface model gives more reasonable results, and is able to explain the effect of small cracks on tensile strength.

DELAMINATION IN TAPERED COMPOSITE WITH DROPPED PLYS

Tests and analysis have been carried out on tapered unidirectional glass fibre-epoxy specimens [14]. Symmetric sections tapered from ten to eight plies with two plies dropped at the mid-plane as shown in Fig. 6a have been investigated under tensile loading. A crack forms in the resin pocket in front of the dropped plies at a relatively low load. Delamination then starts both above and below the ends of the dropped plies. At first there is a small amount of stable

Figure 6. Delamination specimens

delamination, and then rapid propagation occurs. The tapered geometry produces through thickness compression near the ends of the dropped plies, and so this can be considered to be a pure mode II problem.

Similar constant thickness specimens have also been tested which have the same number of continuous and discontinuous plies. Instead of a taper, both ends of the specimens have ten plies, with the two centre plies cut and butted together as shown in Fig. 6b. In some specimens a gap was left between the ends of the cut plies. When tested in tension, the behaviour was very similar to the tapered specimens, but the delamination stress was about 20% lower.

Two problems arise in applying conventional linear elastic fracture mechanics analysis to the tapered specimens. Firstly the strain energy release rate increases with crack length, implying unstable delamination, whereas in the tests some stable delamination occurred. Secondly the strain energy release rate is lower for the tapered specimens than for the constant thickness ones with a gap, yet the delamination stress is higher. Since in both cases the normal stresses at the end of the terminating plies are compressive, the difference cannot be explained in terms of different mode ratios. This suggests a higher mode II propagation fracture energy for the tapered specimens due to the higher through thickness compressive stresses, and friction between the delaminated surfaces is a possible explanation.

This problem was analysed using interface elements between the continuous and discontinuous plies [3]. Friction was included after failure of the interface by applying shear forces resisting relative deformation based on the normal forces and a friction coefficient. A limiting frictional shear stress equal to the shear yield stress was imposed to prevent higher forces arising after interface failure than before. It was found that an excellent fit to the experimental data could be obtained using a mode II fracture energy of 0.87 N/mm, a shear yield stress of 75 MPa, and a friction coefficient of 0.8. This latter value is rather high, suggesting that the increase in effective fracture energy may not in fact be all due to friction effects. Qualitatively the results match the experimental observations very well. At first a small amount of stable delamination was obtained, followed by rapid propagation, as shown in Fig. 7. In contrast linear elastic fracture mechanics predicts unstable crack propagation. The model is also able to explain the much higher delamination stress compared with the constant thickness specimens, since the effect of friction is much higher in the tapered specimens due to the through thickness compression caused by the geometry.

Figure 7. Crack propagation in tapered specimen

CONCLUSIONS

Modelling the interfacial region where delamination occurs is an effective way to analyse mode I and II fracture. It gets around the problem with linear elastic fracture mechanics of requiring an initial crack to be present, and allows more realistic predictions of failure to be made. For cases with long cracks, the results approach those from fracture mechanics because the effect of nonlinearity becomes less important. For cases with short cracks the results approach those from stress based criteria because they are controlled by initiation. The method therefore effectively unifies the stress based and fracture mechanics approaches to failure prediction, and provides a consistent approach that can be applied to a wide variety of practical problems.

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